

The DevSafeOps Dilemma: a Systematic Mapping Study on Rapidity in Safe AD Development - Supplementary Materials

Ali Nouri <i>Volvo Cars</i> Gothenburg, Sweden ali.nouri@volvocars.com	Beatriz Cabrero-Daniel <i>University of Gothenburg, Sweden</i> <i>Department of Computer Science</i> <i>and Engineering</i> beatriz.cabrero-daniel@gu.se	Fredrik Törner <i>Volvo Cars</i> Gothenburg, Sweden fredrik.torner@volvocars.com	Christian Berger <i>University of Gothenburg, Sweden</i> <i>Department of Computer Science</i> <i>and Engineering</i> christian.berger@gu.se
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I. EXTRACTED DATA

Table I and II presents the extracted information about the selected studies in a concise and organized manner, making it easy for readers to review and compare the studies. It includes essential information such as the year of publication, the industry addressed, whether the study is peer-reviewed, or the source of the study. Table I and II provides a useful reference for researchers to gain a better understanding of the field.

II. EXCLUDED STUDIES

On the other hand, Table III, IV, V, and VI lists all the excluded peer-reviewed and some non-peer-reviewed studies, identifying the reasons for their exclusion (rationale). Other excluded records were non-peer-reviewed papers which, as discussed in the study, were excluded due to concerns about their quality, rigour, or use of non-empirical methods.

TABLE I
EXTRACTED INFORMATION ABOUT THE INCLUDED STUDIES (PART I)

Year	Title	Peer reviewed	Source
2018	Data-Centric Communication and Containerization for Future Automotive Software Architectures	Yes	IEEE Xplore
2018	Safely Entering the Deep A Review of Verification and Validation for Machine Learning and a Challenge Elicitation in the automotive industry	Yes	Journal of Automotive Software Engineering
2018	It takes three to tango: Requirement, outcome/data, and AI driven development	Yes	Google Scholar
2018	Requirements engineering in the age of societal-scale cyber-physical systems: The case of automated driving	Yes	IEEE Xplore
2018	Traceability Management with Impact Analysis in DevOps based Software Development	Yes	IEEE Xplore (snowballing)
2018	Contracts for System Design	Yes	IEEE Xplore (snowballing)
2018	SafeScrum@-Agile development of safety-critical software	Yes	IEEE Xplore (snowballing)
2019	Software engineering for automated vehicles addressing the needs of cars that run on software and data	Yes	IEEE Xplore
2019	The Automotive Take on Continuous Experimentation A Multiple Case Study	Yes	IEEE Xplore
2019	Continuous Deployment for Dependable Systems with Continuous Assurance Cases	Yes	IEEE Xplore
2019	A model-driven engineering framework to support the functional safety process	Yes	IEEE Xplore
2019	Software engineering for automated vehicles: Addressing the needs of cars that run on software and data	Yes	Scopus
2020	SafetyOps	No	Google Scholar
2020	UP2DATE: Safe and secure over-the-air software updates on high-performance mixed-criticality systems	Yes	Scopus
2020	Agile safety case and DevOps for the automotive industry	Yes	Scopus
2020	SafeOps: a concept of continuous safety	Yes	IEEE Xplore
2021	Developing SEooC - Original Concepts and Implications when Extending to ADS	Yes	Google Scholar
2021	Towards Establishing Continuous-X Pipeline Using Modular Software-in-the-Loop Test Environments	Yes	SAE Technical Paper series
2021	Test Automation with Grad-CAM Heatmaps - A Future Pipe Segment in MLOps for Vision AI?	Yes	Scopus
2021	(Not) Yet Another Metamodel For Traceability	Yes	Scopus
2021	The AIQ meta-testbed: Pragmatically bridging academic AI testing and industrial Q needs	Yes	Scopus
2022	Architecture as a Backbone for Safe DevOps in Automotive Systems	Yes	IEEE Xplore
2022	An Industrial Experience Report about Challenges from Continuous Monitoring Improvement and Deployment for Autonomous Driving Features	Yes	IEEE Xplore
2022	Continuous Learning Approach to Safety Engineering	Yes	Google Scholar
2022	STPA-Driven Multilevel Runtime Monitoring for In Time Hazard Detection	Yes	Springer
2022	Automating Safety Argument Change Impact Analysis for Machine Learning Components	Yes	IEEE Xplore
2022	DevOps and Safety? SafeOps! Towards Ensuring Safety in Feature-Driven Development with Frequent Releases	Yes	Springer
2022	Towards Continuous Safety Assurance for Autonomous Systems	Yes	IEEE Xplore
2022	A review of testing object-based environment perception for safe automated driving	Yes	Scopus

TABLE II
EXTRACTED INFORMATION ABOUT THE INCLUDED STUDIES (PART II)

Year	Title	Peer reviewed	Source
2023	Development of the System Assurance Reference Model for Generating Modular Assurance Cases	Yes	Scopus
2023	On STPA for Distributed Development of Safe Autonomous Driving: An Interview Study	Yes	Scopus
2023	A Comprehensive Survey on Software as a Service (SaaS) Transformation for the Automotive Systems	Yes	Scopus
2023	Accelerating Digital Transformation: 10 Years of Software Center	Yes	Scopus
2023	Continuous Verification of Automotive Software	Yes	Google Scholar
2023	Synthetic data generation for the continuous development and testing of autonomous construction machinery	Yes	Google Scholar
2023	Continuous Compliance in the Automotive Industry	Yes	IEEE Xplore
2023	Toward a hybrid causal framework for autonomous vehicle safety analysis	Yes	Google Scholar
2023	Towards an AI-driven business development framework: A multi-case study	Yes	Google Scholar
2023	Model Reporting for Certifiable AI: A Proposal from Merging EU Regulation into AI Development	No	Google Scholar
2024	Improving 3D Object Detection for Autonomous Driving – A Case Study of Data-Driven Development	Yes	Google Scholar
2024	Engineering Safety Requirements for Autonomous Driving with Large Language Models	Yes	Google Scholar
2024	Design and Automatic Generation of Safety Cases of ML-Enabled Autonomous Driving Systems	Yes	Google Scholar
2024	Validation of software tools according to ISO 26262 method 1c using continuous practices: applied to the software product TEST-GUIDE	Yes	Google Scholar
2024	Approach for Argumenting Safety on Basis of an Operational Design Domain	Yes	Google Scholar
2024	Welcome Your New AI Teammate: On Safety Analysis by Leashing Large Language Models	Yes	Google Scholar
2024	Integrating scenario- and contract-based verification for automated vessels	Yes	Google Scholar
2024	CausalOps — Towards an industrial lifecycle for causal probabilistic graphical models	Yes	Google Scholar
2024	Enhancing Autonomous Driving Systems through ROS2 and AWS Cloud: V2I Interaction and HPC Data Processing	Yes	Google Scholar
2024	Migration of Model-based Software Components to Service-oriented Architectures	Yes	Google Scholar
2024	Controlling Risk for Highly Automated Transportation Systems Operating in Complex Open Environments: A white paper of the SafeTRANS Closing the Gap Initiative	Yes	Google Scholar
2024	Trustworthiness Assurance Assessment for High-Risk AI-Based Systems	Yes	Google Scholar
2024	An empirical investigation of challenges of specifying training data and runtime monitors for critical software with machine learning and their relation to architectural decisions	Yes	Scopus
2024	Predicting the Type of Road Traffic Accident for Test Scenario Generation	Yes	Google Scholar
2024	Prompting GPT-4 to support automatic safety case generation	Yes	Google Scholar
2024	Trustworthy and collaborative traceability management: Experts' feedback on a blockchain-enabled framework	Yes	Google Scholar
2024	VV Methods Safety Assurance Position Paper	Yes	Google Scholar
2024	Application of Model-Based Systems Engineering Methods in Virtual Homologation Procedures for Automated Driving Functions	Yes	Google Scholar
2024	Requirements and software engineering for automotive perception systems: an interview study	Yes	Scopus
2024	SALIENCE4CAV Public Report: Safety Lifecycle Enabling Continuous Deployment for Connected Automated Vehicles	No	Google Scholar
2024	Artificial intelligence for safety-critical systems in industrial and transportation domains: A survey	Yes	Scopus
2024	Characterizing Software Architectural Metrics for Continuous Compliance in the Automotive Domain	Yes	Scopus
2024	ISTQB® Certified Tester Foundation Level	Yes	Scopus

TABLE III
LIST OF EXCLUDED STUDIES IDENTIFYING THE REASON FOR EXCLUSION (PART I)

Year	Title	Rationale & Exclusion Criteria ID
2024	ADAS and Automated Driving: Systems Engineering	Safety and DevOps are discussed separately in the book (Exc.1). The book is not discussing on challenges or solution of Safety of DevOps (Exc.2).
2024	Perspectives on AI-ML Safety Assurance	The paper is not about the safety of DevOps or Mlops (Exc.1). Moreover the proposed concept is examined for a non automotive context (Exc.1).
2024	A Framework for Managing Quality Requirements for Machine Learning-Based Software Systems	The paper is proposing a framework for requirement management for ML software. The paper does not present any challenge or solution for Handling requirements in DevOps (Exc.2).
2024	The Anatomy of Software-Defined Vehicles Realized for Series with Systems Engineering	The paper is about SDV and focusing on time-to-market, packaging and total cost of ownership. It does not contain solution or challenges for Safety of DevOps for AD (Exc.2).
2024	Vehicle Control Systems: Integrating Edge AI and ML for Enhanced Safety and Performance	The paper is about modular software architecture. The paper is not about DevOps and its safety challenges (Exc.1).
2024	Software Defined Vehicles for Development of Deterministic Services	The paper discuss about SDV, and Service Oriented Architecture, operating systems, virtualization and orchestration techniques and inter- and intra-vehicular communications. The paper is not about safety of DevOps (Exc.1), its challenges or solutions (Exc.2).
2024	Approaches for Automating Cybersecurity Testing of Connected Vehicles	The paper discuss on cybersecurity of connected vehicles. The paper is not about DevOps (Exc.1) and its safety challenges (Exc.2).
2024	Cognitive Load Analysis of Cybersecurity Interfaces in Autonomous Vehicle Control Systems	The paper discuss on human-machine interface (HMI) and cybersecurity aspects of it. The paper is not about DevOps (Exc.1) and its safety challenges (Exc.2).
2024	Cognitive Load Analysis of Cybersecurity Interfaces for Autonomous Vehicle Operators	The paper is about cybersecurity command, control and monitoring interface (CCMI). The paper is not about DevOps (Exc.1) and its safety challenges (Exc.2).
2024	Security Compliance in Model-Driven Software Development	The paper is about cybersecurity of model-driven software development. The paper is not about DevOps (Exc.1) and its safety challenges (Exc.2).
2024	Security and Intelligent Management: Survey	The paper is about security and intelligent management. The paper is not about DevOps (Exc.1) and its safety challenges (Exc.2).
2024	Security and Intelligent 2 Management	duplication of top one.
2024	Integrating Containers and Partitioning Hypervisors for Dependable Real-time Industrial Clouds	The paper discuss on Containers and Partitioning Hypervisors for industrial cloud systems. The paper is not about automotive safety (Exc.1), and it is not clear if the proposed solution is applicable/feasible for DevOps of AD (Exc.2).
2024	A Comprehensive Security Risk Analysis of Cliff Edge on Cyber-Physical Systems	The book chapter discussed the protection threats including concerns in a cyber-physical system. It is not about Safety of DevOps (Exc.1).
2024	IT infrastructure modeling for risk identification and prevention	The thesis is on cyber security and general safety (e.g., fire) risk identification. The thesis is not about safety of DevOps and Automotive (Exc.1).
2024	Mutation testing optimisations using the Clang front-end	The paper discuss on mutation testing. The paper is not on its application in safety of DevOps and automotive (Exc.1).
2024	Continuous Integration of web therapeutical application	The thesis is on testing automation in Web applications. The thesis is not about safety of DevOps and automotive (Exc.1).
2024	Automotive Software Engineering: Grundlagen, Prozesse, Methoden und Werkzeuge	The paper is not in English (Exc.3).
2024	Towards Combining STPA and Safety-Critical Runtime Monitoring	The paper focuses on a PhD plan, outlining research questions without substantial findings on DevSafeOps challenges or solutions (Exc.2).
2024	Rethinking Automotive Software Development: Exploring Software Defined Vehicle and its potential	The thesis focuses on Software Defined Vehicles, not on DevOps in safety-critical AD functions (Exc.1).
2024	Toward a safe MLOps process for the continuous development and safety assurance of ML-based systems in the railway domain	The paper is about MLOps in railway industry. The paper is not discussing about automotive domain (Exc.1).
2024	Safety Concept and Simulation-based Approval of an Automated Driving Function for the Transverse Guidance of Vehicles	The thesis is about safety concepts used for safety argumentation of AD, and focusing on HARA, Simulation based testing, and scenrio based testing. The thesis is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1). It does not identify any challenge in it nor propose solutions for them (Exc.2).

TABLE IV
LIST OF EXCLUDED STUDIES IDENTIFYING THE REASON FOR EXCLUSION (PART II)

Year	Title	Rationale
2023	An investigation of challenges encountered when specifying training data and runtime monitors for safety critical ML applications	Focuses on the safety of machine learning, not safety of MLOps or DevOps (Exc.1).
2023	Safety Assurance of Autonomous Systems using Machine Learning: An Industrial Case Study and Lessons Learnt	The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	Safe AI in the Automotive Domain	This is a summary of a track at conference, and does not present any challenge or solution for safety process in DevOps (Exc.2).
2023	Safe AI in Autonomous Vehicles — SpringerLink	Repeated entry
2023	Accelerating the development of Software Defined Vehicles through Innovative Collaboration across the Industry	The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1)
2023	Human Factors in the Design of Cybersecure Autonomous Vehicle Interfaces — Journal of Bioinformatics and Artificial Intelligence	The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	AUTotech.agil: Architecture and Technologies for Orchestrating Automotive Agility	The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	Towards a security-driven automotive development lifecycle - Dobaj - 2023 - Journal of Software: Evolution and Process - Wiley Online Library	The paper is about Cybersecurity (Exc.1).
2023	AI-Based Predictive Analytics for Autonomous Vehicle Performance Monitoring — Distributed Learning and Broad Applications in Scientific Research	About predictive maintenance for AI and AI challenges. The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	An Ontology and Guidelines for Cybersecurity Risk Assessment in the Automotive Domain	The paper is about TARA and Cybersecurity. The paper is not about safety (Exc.1).
2023	AI-Based Systems for Autonomous Vehicle Night-time Safety and Navigation — Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research and Applications	The paper is about AI to process sensor signal data in low-light scenarios. The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	Reimagining Automotive Service-Oriented Communication: A Case Study on Programmable Data Planes	The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	AI-Based Systems for Autonomous Vehicle Traffic Sign Compliance — Distributed Learning and Broad Applications in Scientific Research	The paper is about traffic sign recognition with AI, but it is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	A compositional approach to creating architecture frameworks with an application to distributed AI systems - ScienceDirect	The paper is about mathematical description for compositional architectural frameworks. The paper is not discussing on DevOps (Exc.1)
2023	An Investigation of Challenges Encountered When Specifying Training Data and Runtime Monitors for Safety Critical ML Applications — SpringerLink	The paper is about AI engineering, focusing on training systems for safety critical applications. The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1)
2023	Computer Safety, Reliability, and Security	This is the collection of papers of SAFECOMP 2023. The included papers are not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	Modeling perception errors in autonomous vehicles and their impact on behavior — NTU Singapore	The PhD thesis is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	Guest editorial: special issue on emerging challenges in software certification and verification — Software Quality Journal	This two pager is describing a special issue and does not present any challenge or solution for Handling requirements in DevOps (Exc.2).
2023	Autonomous Advanced Aerial Mobility—An End-to-End Autonomy Framework for UAVs and Beyond	The paper is not discussing on Automotive, DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	Securing Safety in Collaborative Cyber-Physical Systems through Fault Criticality Analysis	The paper is not discussing on Automotive, DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	[2311.07495] The Last Decade in Review: Tracing the Evolution of Safety Assurance Cases through a Comprehensive Bibliometric Analysis	The paper is not discussing on Automotive, DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	Security and Functional Safety for AI in Embedded Automotive System—A Tutorial	The paper is not discussing on Automotive, DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	On Automotive Electronics — ATZelectronics worldwide	The report is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).

TABLE V
LIST OF EXCLUDED STUDIES IDENTIFYING THE REASON FOR EXCLUSION (PART III)

Year	Title	Rationale
2023	AI-Based Systems for Autonomous Vehicle Driver Monitoring and Alertness — Journal of AI in Healthcare and Medicine	The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	AI in the Automotive Industry — SpringerLink	This book chapter does not present any challenge or solution for DevOps in safety process of automotive (Exc.2).
2023	Evaluating Artificial Neural Network Robustness for Safety-Critical Systems — Welcome to DTU Research Database	The PhD thesis on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	Robustness Evaluation for Safety-Critical Systems Utilizing Artificial Neural Network Classifiers in Operation: A Survey by Jin Zhang, Jingyue Li, Josef Oehmen :: SSRN	The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	Neural Network-Based Classification of Electric Vehicle Acceleration Pedal Signals: From Training to Microcontroller Deployment - Webthesis	The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	Lessons Learned Building a Tool for Workflow+	The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	SINTEF Open: Reporting of incidents in automated systems during drilling operations	The report is not discussing on automotive, DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	Context modeling for cyber-physical systems	The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	A Knowledge Management Strategy for Seamless Compliance with the Machinery Regulation	The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps in automotive domain (Exc.1).
2023	MLOps Spanning Whole Machine Learning Life Cycle: A Survey	The paper is not discussing in ML for automotive domain (Exc.1). Moreover, no specific challenge or solution is proposed for safety of DevOps (Exc.2).
2023	Understanding and Managing Non-Functional Requirements for Machine Learning Systems - ProQuest	The report is not discussing on automotive, DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	Secure and Efficient NVM Usage for Embedded Systems Using AES-128 and Huffman Compression — The European Journal of Research and Development	The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	Table of Contents	This table of contents is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	Designing Resilient Cybersecurity Architectures for Autonomous Vehicles - Lessons from Complex Adaptive Systems: Draws lessons from complex adaptive systems to design resilient cybersecurity architectures for AVs — African Journal of Artificial Intelligen	The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	The impact of using a contract-driven, test-interceptor based software development approach	The PhD thesis is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	An Exploratory Study of V-Model in Building ML-Enabled Software: A Systems Engineering Perspective	The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	Automotive Software Engineering	The slide is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2023	Compliance and Audit Challenges in DevOps: A Security Perspective	The paper is not discussing on safety (Exc.1).
2022	Taxonomy of Machine Learning Safety A Survey and Primer	The paper is not discussing on safety of DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2022	ACIA A Methodology for identification of Architectural Design Patterns that support Continuous Integration based on Continuous Assessment	The paper is not discussing on safety (Exc.1).
2022	Intelligence Driven Software Performance Assurance	The PhD thesis is not discussing on safety of DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2022	Improving Documentation Agility in Safety Critical Software Systems Development For Aerospace	Is about aerospace with the need for further investigation on the applicability of the solution in the automotive industry and validation through industry case studies.
2022	Towards an AI driven business development framework A multi case study	Discusses AI in general with some content on MLOps and safety. The paper is not discussing on safety of DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1). It does not identify any challenges nor propose solutions for them (Exc.2).
2021	Building Secure Cars: Assuring the Software Development Lifecycle	The paper focuses on cybersecurity, not DevOps or safety-critical aspects in AD development (Exc.1).
2021	Developing and Operating Artificial Intelligence Models in Trustworthy Autonomous Systems	The paper discuss on trustworthiness of autonomous systems in DevOps. The paper is not discussing on safety (Exc.1).

TABLE VI
LIST OF EXCLUDED STUDIES IDENTIFYING THE REASON FOR EXCLUSION (PART IV)

Year	Title	Rationale
2020	Towards a Taxonomy for Eliciting Design Operation Continuum Requirements of Cyber Physical Systems	The paper is on CPS requirement engineering with a railway industry case study. The paper is not discussing on safety (Exc.1).
2021	Towards a continuous certification of safety critical avionics software	The paper is on avionics method. The paper is not discussing on automotive and safety (Exc.1).
2020	DevOps in an ISO Regulated Environment A Multivocal Literature Review	The paper is on DevOps for medical devices. The paper is not discussing on automotive and safety (Exc.1).
2020	A Continuous Certification Methodology for DevOps	The paper is not discussing on automotive and safety (Exc.1). It does not identify any challenge in it nor propose solutions for them (Exc.2).
2020	Fast track lifecycle using SafeScrum and The Agile Safety Case	The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2020	Integration of Security Standards in DevOps Pipelines: An Industry Case Study	The paper is not discussing on automotive and safety (Exc.1).
2020	Continuous Experimentation for Automotive Software on the Example of a Heavy Commercial Vehicle in Daily Operation	The paper is on a prove of concept heavy vehicle experimentation. It does not identify any challenge in it nor propose solutions for them (Exc.2).
2023	Seven Lessons Learned From Automotive Software Supplier Collaborations	The paper is not discussing on safety (Exc.1).
2021	Proposing a Framework for Impact Analysis for Low Code Development Platforms	The paper is not discussing on safety and automotive (Exc.1).
2015	Service Dependability with Continuously Revised Assurance Cases by Multiple Stakeholders A Case Study	The paper is on education services. The paper is not discussing on automotive safety-critical applications (Exc.1).
2021	DDI A novel technology and innovation model for dependable collaborative and autonomous systems	The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2019	Industrial Perspective on Reuse of Safety Artifacts in Software Product Lines	The paper focuses on reusing components and artifacts in new projects, not continuously changing components. The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1). Only a small part discusses integrating safety, which requires further research, however it does not identify any challenge nor propose solutions for them (Exc.2).
2021	Security Debt: Characteristics, Product Life-Cycle Integration and Items	The paper focuses on security technical debt. The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2021	Requirement Engineering Challenges for AI intense Systems Development	The paper is not discussing on safety (Exc.1).
2020	A case study of agile software development for safety Critical systems projects	It is not related to the automotive industry.
2016	Agile safety case for vehicle trial operations	It provides an oversimplified safety case for low-speed AD in Agile way of working. It does not consider high-speed AD and customer vehicles in the context of safety standards. The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1). It does not identify any challenge nor propose solutions for them (Exc.2).
2020	A Preliminary View on Automotive Cyber Security Management Systems	The paper is not discussing on DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2020	Scenarios in the Loop Integrated Requirements Analysis and Automotive System Validation	Discusses devOps and safety separately. It does not identify any challenges nor propose solutions for them (Exc.2).
2021	Machine Learning Development Audit Framework Assessment and Inspection of Risk and Quality of Data Model and Development Process	The paper is not discussing on safety of DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2016	Organic Evolution of Development Organizations An Experience Report	The paper is not discussing on safety of DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2019	On the Nature of Automotive Service Architectures	The paper is not discussing on safety of DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2017	Deliverable Internet of Things Risk Analysis and Assessment	The paper is not discussing on safety of DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2021	Exploring the Assessment List for Trustworthy AI in the Context of Advanced Driver Assistance Systems	The paper is not discussing on safety of DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2021	ADS Safety Assurance Future Directions	The paper is not discussing on safety of DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).
2019	Software Verification and Validation Technologies and Tools	The paper is not discussing on safety of DevOps nor MLOps (Exc.1).